

On the Runtime Analysis of Reinforcement Learning Hyper-Heuristics

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Abstract. Selection Hyper-heuristics (HHs) automate algorithmic design by selecting from a set of low-level heuristics which one to apply at each stage of the optimisation process. Several impressive results have been recently rigorously proven regarding the performance of selection hyper-heuristics (HHs) for standard benchmark functions. However, the learning mechanisms employed by these HHs are considerably simplified compared to the machine learning techniques typically employed in real world applications. In this paper we analyse a Reinforcement Learning Hyper-heuristic (RLHH) from the literature. The only previous result available proved that for a wide range of parameter settings, RLHH does not learn to select parameters appropriately for the standard LEADINGONES benchmark function. In this paper we rigorously prove that with appropriate parameter values RLHH equipped with two random local search operators, RLS_1 and RLS_2 optimises the benchmark function in the best possible expected runtime achievable with the two operators up to lower order terms. Experiments show that for realistic problem sizes it is faster than the Generalised Random Gradient HH which was previously proven to also have optimal runtime up to lower order terms.

Keywords: Hyper-heuristics · Reinforcement Learning · Runtime Analysis · Theory

1 Introduction

Hyper-heuristics (HHs) are automated algorithm design techniques for optimisation problems [8, 42, 20]. They work at a higher level of abstraction than randomised search heuristics by either generating offline a heuristic for the problem at hand using heuristic components (*generation* HH) or online by selecting which heuristic to apply directly at each stage of the optimisation process from a set of available low level heuristics (*selection* HH). The aim is to relieve the practitioner of the task of identifying which algorithm and related parameter settings to apply to the given optimisation problem. Furthermore, different heuristics, or even different parameter settings may perform better at different stages of the optimisation process.

Numerous successful applications of HH have been reported in several domains [34, 44, 45, 29, 26, 1, 25, 7]. Although the field building a theoretical understanding of HHs is still in its infancy, several advances have been made recently

regarding the theoretical foundations of selection HHs [32, 33, 4, 17, 15]. See [38] for a survey earlier results.

Selection HHs typically consist of two components: 1) a heuristic methodology, also referred to as the *learning mechanism*, that selects which heuristic to be applied in the next step, and 2) a move-acceptance methodology to decide whether to accept the new solution. Concerning the move acceptance component it has been shown how simple move acceptance hyper-heuristics (MAHH) are very effective at escaping local optima. The MAHH switching with some probability p between an elitist strict improvement acceptance rule and a non-elitist rule that accepts any generated solution can optimise the standard CLIFF_d benchmark function in the best known expected runtime of $O(n^3/d^2 + n \log n)$ [32]. A variant of the MAHH that switches between accepting strict improvements and only accepting worsening moves has been shown to optimise the JUMP_m function in expected $O((n^3/m) \log n)$ function evaluations [4]; again this is the best known expected runtime for the function class.

Impressive results have also been shown when the performance of the HH depends on the learning mechanism used to determine the most appropriate low-level heuristic to be applied at each stage of the optimisation process. In particular, the Generalised Random Gradient (GRG) HH has been proven to optimise the standard LEADINGONES benchmark function in the optimal expected runtime (up to the leading constant) achievable by any unary unbiased search heuristic if equipped with a sufficient number of low-level Randomised Local Search (RLS) heuristics [31]. Since the result depends on setting its *learning period* τ parameter appropriately, an Adaptive Random Gradient (ARG) was introduced later that also runs in optimal expected runtime, dispensing the user from having to identify an appropriate value for τ [16]. These algorithms have also been shown to be effective for other classes of functions [30]. Indeed, GRG has the best known expected runtime for the multimodal TWORATES benchmark function [33].

All the mentioned HHs use very simple learning mechanisms, the most sophisticated being the random gradient one that selects an operator uniformly at random and continues applying it so long as the operator succeeds at identifying an improving solution within the learning period τ . These, however, are very different from the more sophisticated machine learning mechanisms typically employed by HHs in real-world applications [43, 11, 41, 9, 37, 35, 3, 40, 5, 19, 23]. One exception is the work by Alanazi and Lehre [2] which analysed a reinforcement learning HH (RLHH) from the HH literature [37]. The RLHH assigns weights to each low level heuristic which are increased by a rewarding additive factor α if the applied heuristic identifies an improvement and are decreased by a penalty factor β otherwise. Then the operator to be applied is decided at each step via roulette wheel selection.

The analysis of Alanazi and Lehre though only provided negative results by focusing on identifying parameter ranges for which the RLHH is inefficient. In particular, they analysed the RLHH for the LEADINGONES benchmark function equipped with m low-level heuristics among which only one has a positive

Algorithm 1 REINFORCEMENT LEARNING HYPER-HEURISTIC (RLHH) [37, 2]

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1: procedure RLHH( $\alpha, \beta, w_{\min}, w_{\max}, w$ )
2:    $s \leftarrow \text{Unif}(\mathcal{S}); w_{[m]}^{(0)} \leftarrow w$ 
3:   while stopping conditions not satisfied do
4:     Pick  $i \in [m]$ , with probability  $p_i^{(t)} = \frac{w_i^{(t)}}{\sum_{j=1}^m w_j^{(t)}}$ 
5:      $s' \leftarrow h_i(s)$ 
6:      $w_i^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \begin{cases} \min(w_i^{(t)} + \alpha, w_{\max}), & \text{if } f(s') > f(s) \\ \max(w_i^{(t)} - \beta, w_{\min}), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ 
7:     if  $f(s') > f(s)$  then
8:        $s \leftarrow s'$ 
9:   return  $s$ 

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probability of identifying improvements. In this scenario they derived parameter settings for which the RLHH provably cannot distinguish the effective operator from the rest, thus runs in the same expected runtime as an algorithm that at each step selects an operator uniformly at random (i.e., *simple random* HH [12]).

In this paper we aim to start building the theoretical foundations of HH using reinforcement learning mechanisms. We prove that with appropriate parameter settings the RLHH equipped with two operators, RLS₁ which flips one bit and RLS₂ which flips two bits without replacement, runs in the best possible expected runtime achievable using the two operators (i.e. $\approx 0.42329n^2$) for LEADINGONES. An experimental analysis reveals that RLHH is slightly faster than the GRG HH and slightly slower than ARG for realistic problem sizes.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, we formally define the Reinforcement Learning Hyper-Heuristic (RLHH) algorithm and the benchmark function used for the analysis. We also introduce the mathematical tools that will be used in our runtime analysis.

2.1 Algorithm

The Reinforcement Learning Hyper-heuristic (RLHH) framework analyzed in this work is a selection hyper-heuristic that dynamically manages a portfolio of m low-level heuristics $H = \{h_1, \dots, h_m\}$. Unlike static selection mechanisms, RLHH aims to automatically learn the optimal heuristic to be applied at different stages of the optimization process by maintaining a weight w_i for each heuristic.

The pseudocode for the RLHH framework as considered in [2] is given in Algorithm 1. At each iteration, the algorithm selects a heuristic h_i with a probability proportional to its current weight $p_i = w_i / \sum_{j=1}^m w_j$. If the applied heuristic generates a strict fitness improvement (i.e., $f(s') > f(s)$), it is rewarded by increasing its weight by an additive factor α , capped at a maximum value w_{\max} . Conversely, if the heuristic fails to strictly improve the fitness, it is penalized by

subtracting a factor β , bounded below by w_{\min} . Other choices for the update rules (e.g., multiplicative updates rather than additive) and for the selection rules (e.g., selecting the heuristic with highest weight i.e., *max choice*) have been applied in the literature. Here we follow the scheme analysed by Alanazi and Lehre described in Algorithm 1 [2].

In our analysis, we consider a portfolio of two standard mutation operators (i.e., $m = 2$) commonly used in evolutionary algorithms for pseudo-Boolean optimization; $h_1 = \text{RLS}_1$ which flips exactly one bit chosen uniformly at random, while $h_2 = \text{RLS}_2$ flips exactly two distinct bits chosen uniformly at random.

We configure the RLHH parameters as follows. Reward factor $\alpha = 1 + 1/\log n$, penalty factor $\beta = 1/n$, initial weight $w_1^{(0)} = w_2^{(0)} = \log n$, upper bound $w_{\max} = \frac{n}{\log^{1+\gamma} n}$, where $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ is a strictly positive constant and lower bound $w_{\min} = 1$. The only available runtime analysis of the RLHH has shown that if the parameters are set such that α is at most as large as β (i.e. $\alpha \leq \beta$), then the HH will not be able to distinguish between the low level heuristics, thus at each step chooses one uniformly at random [2]. For the hyper-heuristic to be effective, the reward factor α should be able to counteract the weight decrease due to the expected number of failures before a success. Considering that a basic randomised local search heuristic (i.e., RLS_1) always has an improvement probability of at least $1/n$ unless it is trapped on a local optima, thus succeeds in n expected steps, we set the penalty factor to $\beta = 1/n$ and the reward factor to $\alpha = 1 + 1/\log n$ (slightly larger than n times β). Thus, as long as the HH is not trapped on a local optima the weight of RLS_1 always increases in expectation. Yet, if some other low-level heuristic has a higher success probability, its weight will increase faster. Since the operators are all initialised with the same weight value, we let the initial weight grow slightly with the problem size (i.e., $w_1^{(0)} = w_2^{(0)} = \log n$) so that the first operator to improve does not gain a large weight advantage which may strongly bias (maybe incorrectly) the process in its favour. An upper bound on the weights, w_{\max} , is required so that when the best operator for the current optimisation stage changes, the time for the respective weights to increase and decrease will not be too large. At the same time w_{\max} should also not be too small, to avoid that the weight of RLS_1 eventually catches up with that of the current best operator by reaching the upper bound due to its positive drift (by design). In this case it would not be possible to distinguish the weights because, once at the boundary, the weight of the best operator cannot increase further. Our analyses will show that with a setting of $w_{\max} = \frac{n}{\log^{1+\gamma} n}$, $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ a constant, the RLHH optimises LEADINGONES in optimal expected runtime up to lower order terms. The lower bound on the weight can be simply set to any constant and we choose $w_{\min} = 1$.

2.2 Benchmark Function

We analyze the performance of the RLHH on the same standard pseudo-Boolean benchmark function LEADINGONES (LO) used in the previous work in the liter-

ature [2]. The function is defined over the search space $\mathcal{S} = \{0, 1\}^n$ as

$$\text{LO}(s) = \sum_{i=1}^n \prod_{j=1}^i s_j.$$

where s_j is the value of the j_{th} bit in the bit string s . The LO value of a bit-string is the number of consecutive leading 1-bits in the bit-string, thus the global optimum is the all-ones string $s^* = (1, \dots, 1)$.

To successfully improve a candidate solution s with current fitness $\text{LO}(s) = i < n$, an algorithm must necessarily mutate the $(i + 1)$ -th bit (the first 0-bit in the string). Any mutations applied to the leading prefix of i ones will destroy the prefix and strictly decrease the fitness. Meanwhile, mutations applied to the trailing suffix (bits from position $i + 2$ to n) are entirely invisible to the current fitness evaluation, acting as neutral moves. The unbiased black box complexity of LEADINGONES is $\Theta(n^2)$ [27] and evolutionary algorithms using standard bit mutation match this performance. The standard (1+1) EA (with mutation rate $\frac{1}{n}$) has an expected runtime of $\frac{\epsilon-1}{2}n^2 - o(n^2) \approx 0.85914n^2 - o(n^2)$ [6]. By implementing a fitness-dependent mutation rate, the expected runtime of the (1+1) EA decreases to $\approx (1 \pm o(1))0.68n^2$ [6]. RLS₁ has an expected runtime of $0.5n^2$ fitness function evaluations [10]. The best expected runtime achievable by unbiased (1+1) black box algorithms is $\approx (1 \pm o(1))0.388n^2$ [18, 13]. The Generalised Random Gradient (GRG) and the Adaptive Random Gradient selection HHs with a sufficiently large constant sized low level heuristic set $|H| = k = O(1)$ have been shown to match this optimal performance [31, 16]. If the heuristic set is limited to $|H| = \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$, then the best possible expected runtime is $(1 + o(1)) \cdot 0.42329n^2$ [31]. Here we show that RLHH matches this optimal performance.

2.3 Mathematical Tools

To rigorously analyze the expected runtime and the stochastic dynamics of the weight adaptation mechanism of the RLHH algorithm, we rely on several fundamental tools from probability theory and stochastic processes.

Theorem 1 (Chernoff Bounds [36]). *Let $X = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i$ be the sum of independent Poisson trials such that $\mathbb{E}[X] = \mu$. Then for any $0 < \delta < 1$*

$$\Pr(X \leq (1 - \delta)\mu) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{\delta^2\mu}{2}\right),$$

and for any $\delta > 0$,

$$\Pr(X \geq (1 + \delta)\mu) \leq \left(\frac{e^\delta}{(1 + \delta)^{1+\delta}}\right)^\mu.$$

Theorem 2 (Doob's Maximal Inequality [21]). *Let $(Z_t)_{t \geq 0}$ be a stochastic process adapted to a filtration $(\mathcal{F}_t)_{t \geq 0}$. For any constant $\delta > 0$,*

- (i) **Submartingale bound:** If $(Z_t)_{t \geq 0}$ is a non-negative submartingale, then for any finite time horizon $T \geq 0$, the probability that the maximum of the process reaches or exceeds δ is bounded by

$$\Pr \left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} Z_t \geq \delta \right) \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[Z_T]}{\delta}.$$

- (ii) **Supermartingale bound:** If $(Z_t)_{t \geq 0}$ is a non-negative supermartingale, then the probability that the supremum of the process reaches or exceeds δ over infinite time is bounded by

$$\Pr \left(\sup_{t \geq 0} Z_t \geq \delta \right) \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[Z_0]}{\delta}.$$

Theorem 3 (Freedman's Inequality[22]). Let $(Y_t)_{t \geq 1}$ be a martingale difference sequence with respect to a filtration $(\mathcal{F}_t)_{t \geq 0}$. Suppose there exists a constant R such that $Y_t \leq R$ almost surely for all $t \geq 1$. Let $M_k = \sum_{t=1}^k Y_t$ be the associated martingale, and let $V_k = \sum_{t=1}^k \text{Var}(Y_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1})$ be the predictable quadratic variation. For any $\Delta > 0$ and $v > 0$,

$$\Pr(\exists k \geq 1 : M_k \geq \Delta \text{ and } V_k \leq v) \leq \exp \left(-\frac{\Delta^2}{2(v + R\Delta/3)} \right).$$

Theorem 4 (Additive Drift Theorem[24, 28]). Let $(X_t)_{t \geq 0}$ be a stochastic process adapted to a filtration $(\mathcal{F}_t)_{t \geq 0}$ over a state space $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathbb{R}$. Let T be the first hitting time of the region $(-\infty, a]$. If $X_0 \geq a$ and there exists a constant $\delta > 0$ such that for all $t < T$, $\mathbb{E}[X_t - X_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] \geq \delta$, then

$$\mathbb{E}[T | X_0] \leq \frac{X_0 - a}{\delta}.$$

Theorem 5 (Law of Total Expectation / Tower Property [36]). Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \Pr)$ be a probability space, and let \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{F}_2 be two sub- σ -algebras of \mathcal{F} such that $\mathcal{F}_1 \subseteq \mathcal{F}_2$. For any random variable X with finite expectation ($\mathbb{E}[|X|] < \infty$), it holds almost surely that:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{F}_2] | \mathcal{F}_1] = \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{F}_1].$$

In the context of discrete-time stochastic processes with a natural filtration $(\mathcal{F}_t)_{t \geq 0}$, this implies that for any time steps $s \leq t$, conditioning on the historical state \mathcal{F}_s absorbs the intermediate conditioning on \mathcal{F}_t ,

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{F}_t] | \mathcal{F}_s] = \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{F}_s].$$

2.4 Notation

Throughout this paper, the optimization process is modeled as a discrete-time stochastic process. We denote the current time step, which exactly corresponds

to the number of fitness evaluations, by $t \in \mathbb{N}_0$, and the candidate solution maintained by the algorithm at step t by $s^{(t)} \in \{0, 1\}^n$. The fitness value of the current solution is typically denoted by $i = \text{LO}(s^{(t)})$. To rigorously ground our probabilistic arguments, we let \mathcal{F}_t be the natural filtration representing the complete historical trajectory of the algorithmic state (including all past solutions, weights, and operator selections) up to step t .

Regarding the operator selection mechanism, $w_j^{(t)}$ represents the current weight of heuristic h_j (where $j \in \{1, 2\}$ respectively correspond to RLS₁ and RLS₂), and $p_j^{(t)} = w_j^{(t)} / (w_1^{(t)} + w_2^{(t)})$ defines the selection probability of that heuristic at step t . Furthermore, we define $P_j(i)$ as the *success* probability that applying heuristic h_j to a solution with fitness i yields a strict fitness improvement. Finally, Δ_j^{sel} denotes the conditional expected one-step change in the weight of heuristic h_j , given that it was selected for application at the current step. We say that an event occurs *asymptotically almost surely* (a.a.s.) if its probability is at least $1 - o(1)$.

3 RLHH has Optimal Runtime for Leading Ones

In this section, we rigorously prove that the RLHH algorithm achieves the optimal expected runtime for the LEADINGONES function. To understand the algorithmic dynamics, we first evaluate the state-dependent success probabilities of the two mutation operators at any given fitness level $i = \text{LO}(s)$.

For operator RLS₁, a strict fitness improvement occurs if and only if the first 0-bit is flipped. Thus, its success probability is uniformly bounded by $P_1(i) = 1/n$. For operator RLS₂, a success requires flipping the first 0-bit alongside any of the $n - i - 1$ trailing bits. The exact probability of this joint event evaluates to:

$$P_2(i) = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{n-i-1}{n-1} + \frac{n-i-1}{n} \cdot \frac{1}{n-1} = \frac{2(n-i-1)}{n(n-1)}.$$

Comparing these transition probabilities reveals a strict phase transition in the optimal search strategy. Solving $P_2(i) > P_1(i)$ yields $i < n/2$. Consequently, RLS₂ is preferable during the first half of the search space, whereas RLS₁ becomes more effective once $i > n/2$. As established in the literature, the optimal strategy for an algorithm equipped with these two operators is to apply RLS₂ exclusively for optimizing the first $n/2$ bits, and then permanently switch to RLS₁ for the remainder of the optimization [31].

To demonstrate that the RLHH algorithm learns and executes this optimal operator sequence a.a.s., we divide our mathematical analysis into three subsequent subsections. First, we analyze Phase 1 ($i < n/2$), proving that the parameter adaptation mechanism rapidly establishes a strict dominance of RLS₂ a.a.s. during the initial stage of optimization. Next, we examine Phase 2 ($i \geq n/2$), demonstrating that as the fitness crosses the theoretical threshold, the algorithm successfully reverses its weight distribution to maintain the absolute dominance of RLS₁ a.a.s.. Finally, we synthesize the bounded times from these two distinct

phases to compute the total expected optimization time, concluding that RLHH has the optimal expected runtime up to a lower-order $o(n^2)$ term.

3.1 Dominance of RLS₂ in Phase 1

In this subsection, we analyze the runtime behavior of the RLHH algorithm on the LEADINGONES problem during Phase 1, defined as the interval where the fitness satisfies $0 \leq \text{LO}(s) < \frac{n}{2}$. In this region, the operator RLS₂ possesses a higher success probability than the operator RLS₁. The analysis demonstrates that the dynamic weight adaptation mechanism successfully identifies and exploits RLS₂ with a selection probability of $p_2 = 1 - o(1)$, incurring an $o(n^2)$ time overhead compared to the optimal expected runtime.

The stochastic dynamics of Phase 1 are established through a sequence of supporting lemmata. First, Lemma 1 derives the conditional drifts of the operator weights based on their state-dependent success probabilities, showing that when the respective operators are selected w_2 grows asymptotically faster than w_1 in expectation. Lemma 2 ensures that the selection probability $p_2^{(t)}$ remains bounded away from zero for Phase 1. Building on this, Lemma 3 proves that the weight w_2 rapidly reaches its upper limit $w_{\max} = \frac{n}{\log^{1+\gamma} n}$ within an $o(n^2)$ time overhead. Concurrently, Lemma 4 constructs a non-negative supermartingale to bound the multiplicative growth of w_1 during the climbing stage of w_2 , ensuring w_1 remains sub-polynomial. Finally, Lemma 5 applies the law of total expectation, Doob's inequality and Freedman's inequality to show the dominance of RLS₂ is robustly maintained a.a.s. until the fitness reaches $n/2$.

We put everything together in Theorem 6 to formally establish that RLHH optimises the first $n/2$ leading ones in expected time $T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} + o(n^2)$, where $T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}}$ is the exact expected hitting time for the pure RLS₂ algorithm to traverse the same fitness distance.

We start by analysing the expected single-step changes of the operator weights conditional on the operators being selected for reproduction.

Lemma 1. *For the RLHH algorithm with reward parameter $\alpha = 1 + 1/\log n$ and penalty parameter $\beta = 1/n$ optimizing the LEADINGONES function, let Δ_1^{sel} and Δ_2^{sel} denote the expected one-step weight changes of the operators RLS₁ and RLS₂, conditioned on being selected. The weight drifts satisfy*

$$\Delta_1^{\text{sel}} = \frac{1}{n \log n} + \frac{1}{n^2}, \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta_2^{\text{sel}} = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{n}\right).$$

Furthermore, for any fitness level $i \leq n/2 - \epsilon n$ with a constant $\epsilon > 0$, there exists a constant $c > 0$ such that the weight drift of RLS₂ is lower-bounded by

$$\Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{c}{n}.$$

Proof. Let $P_j(i)$ be the probability of RLS_j improving a solution with i leading ones. By definition, the expected weight change when operator j is selected is

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_j^{\text{sel}}(i) &= \mathbb{E}\left[w_j^{(t+1)} - w_j^{(t)} \mid j \text{ is selected, LO}(s) = i\right] \\ &= \alpha P_j(i) - \beta(1 - P_j(i)) = (\alpha + \beta)P_j(i) - \beta.\end{aligned}$$

The success probability of RLS_1 is $P_1(i) = \frac{1}{n}$, and for RLS_2 it is $P_2(i) = \frac{2(n-i-1)}{n(n-1)}$. Substituting $\alpha = 1 + 1/\log n$ and $\beta = 1/n$ yields

$$\Delta_1^{\text{sel}}(i) = (\alpha + \beta) \cdot \frac{1}{n} - \beta = \frac{1}{n \log n} + \frac{1}{n^2}.$$

For RLS_2 , we have

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_2^{\text{sel}}(i) &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{\log n} + \frac{1}{n}\right) \cdot P_2(i) - \frac{1}{n} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{n} + \frac{2}{n} \left(\frac{1}{\log n} + \frac{1}{n}\right) = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{n}\right),\end{aligned}$$

where we used that $P_2(i) \leq 2/n$.

For $i \leq \frac{n}{2} - \epsilon n$, $P_2(i)$ is greater than $P_1(i)$. Specifically, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_2^{\text{sel}}(i) &= \frac{n-1-2i}{n(n-1)} + \frac{2(n-i-1)}{n(n-1)} \left(\frac{1}{\log n} + \frac{1}{n}\right) \\ &\geq \frac{2\epsilon n - 1}{n(n-1)} + \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{1}{\log n} + \frac{1}{n}\right) \\ &= \frac{2\epsilon n - 1}{n(n-1)} + \Delta_1^{\text{sel}}(i) \geq \frac{c}{n},\end{aligned}$$

for some constant $c > 0$. □

By defining a composite process $U_t = 2w_2^{(t)} - w_1^{(t)}$ and constructing an exponential potential function $Z_t = \exp(-\lambda U_t)$ that operates as a non-negative supermartingale, we rigorously bound the probability that w_1 ever exceeds twice the value of w_2 over a polynomial time horizon by applying Doob's maximal inequality (Theorem 2) to Z_t .

Lemma 2. *For the RLHH algorithm optimizing the LEADINGONES function with initial weights $w_1^{(0)} = w_2^{(0)} = \log n$, consider a polynomial time horizon $T = \text{poly}(n)$. Assuming the fitness satisfies $\text{LO}(s^{(t)}) \leq n/2 - \epsilon n$ for a constant $\epsilon > 0$ for all $t \leq T$, the probability that $w_1^{(t)} \geq 2w_2^{(t)}$ occurs at any step $t \in [0, T]$ is bounded by*

$$\Pr\left(\exists t \in [0, T] : w_1^{(t)} \geq 2w_2^{(t)}\right) = n^{-\Omega(1)}.$$

Proof. We define the distance process $U_t = 2w_2^{(t)} - w_1^{(t)}$. The event $w_1^{(t)} \geq 2w_2^{(t)}$ occurs if and only if $U_t \leq 0$. The weights are initialized to $w_1^{(0)} = w_2^{(0)} = \log n$, giving $U_0 = \log n$.

As long as $U_t > 0$, we have $p_2^{(t)} > 1/3$ and $p_1^{(t)} < 2/3$. Using Lemma 1, the expected drift of U_t conditioned on the filtration \mathcal{F}_t is bounded from below by a constant $c_1 > 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\Delta U_t \mid \mathcal{F}_t] &= 2\mathbb{E}[\Delta w_2^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] - \mathbb{E}[\Delta w_1^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= 2p_2^{(t)} \Delta_2^{\text{sel}} - p_1^{(t)} \Delta_1^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{c}{n} - \frac{1}{3} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\log n} + \frac{1}{n^2} \right) \geq \frac{c_1}{n}. \end{aligned}$$

The maximum single-step change is bounded by $R = 2\alpha \leq 4$. The conditional second moment is bounded by the maximum success probability $2/n$ and the failure penalty $\beta = 1/n$. Thus, we have

$$\mathbb{E}[(\Delta U_t)^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq \frac{2}{n}(4)^2 + 1 \cdot \left(\frac{4}{n^2} \right) \leq \frac{c_2}{n},$$

for some constant $c_2 > 0$.

We introduce the potential function $Z_t = \exp(-\lambda U_t)$ for a constant $\lambda > 0$. We bound the conditional expectation of Z_{t+1} using the inequality $e^x \leq 1 + x + \frac{x^2}{2} e^{|x|}$. Since $|\lambda \Delta U_t| \leq 4\lambda$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[Z_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] &= Z_t \cdot \mathbb{E}[\exp(-\lambda \Delta U_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &\leq Z_t \left(1 - \lambda \mathbb{E}[\Delta U_t \mid \mathcal{F}_t] + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} \mathbb{E}[(\Delta U_t)^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_t] e^{4\lambda} \right) \\ &\leq Z_t \left(1 - \lambda \frac{c_1}{n} + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} \frac{c_2}{n} e^{4\lambda} \right) \\ &= Z_t \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{n} \left(c_1 - \frac{\lambda c_2}{2} e^{4\lambda} \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Since $c_1, c_2 > 0$, we can choose a sufficiently small constant $\lambda > 0$ such that $\frac{\lambda c_2}{2} e^{4\lambda} \leq c_1$. For this λ , we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}[Z_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq Z_t,$$

which proves that Z_t is a non-negative supermartingale.

Applying Doob's Maximal Inequality, the probability that $U_t \leq 0$ at any time t is bounded by the probability that $Z_t \geq 1$,

$$\Pr(\exists t \geq 0 : U_t \leq 0) = \Pr(\exists t \geq 0 : Z_t \geq 1) \leq \mathbb{E}[Z_0].$$

With $U_0 = \log n$, we have $\mathbb{E}[Z_0] = \exp(-\lambda \log n) = n^{-\lambda/\ln 2}$. Since $\lambda > 0$ is a constant, the failure probability is bounded by $n^{-\Omega(1)}$. \square

To prove that the RLHH algorithm achieves the optimal Phase 1 runtime in Theorem 6, the selection probability of RLS₂ must rapidly approach 1. We first show that the weight w_2 climbs to its upper bound w_{\max} in $o(n^2)$ steps with probability $1 - o(1)$. Within this time with overwhelming probability at most $\frac{n}{2} - \epsilon n$ leading ones are optimized for a constant $\epsilon > 0$. Lemma 1, thus ensures an $\Omega(1/n)$ drift for w_2 during the climbing stage.

Lemma 3. *For the RLHH algorithm optimizing the LEADINGONES function with parameter $w_{\max} = \frac{n}{\log^{1+\gamma} n}$ for a constant $\gamma > 0$, with probability at least $1 - \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^{\gamma/2} n}\right)$, the weight w_2 reaches w_{\max} within $t_{\max} = \frac{n^2}{\log^{1+\gamma/2} n}$ steps, and the fitness satisfies $\text{LO}(s^{(t)}) \leq n/2 - \epsilon n$ during this entire climbing period.*

Proof. We define the stopping time $\tau = \min\{t \geq 0 \mid w_1^{(t)} \geq 2w_2^{(t)} \text{ or } \text{LO}(s^{(t)}) > n/2 - \epsilon n\}$, since by Lemma 2 the probability that $w_1^{(t)} \geq 2w_2^{(t)}$ occurs within any polynomial time is at most $n^{-\Omega(1)}$.

For any $t < \tau$, the condition $w_1^{(t)} < 2w_2^{(t)}$ guarantees $p_2^{(t)} > 1/3$ and $\Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \geq c/n$ by Lemma 1. The expected one-step drift of w_2 given the filtration \mathcal{F}_t is

$$\mathbb{E}[w_2^{(t+1)} - w_2^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t, t < \tau] = p_2^{(t)} \Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{c}{3n}.$$

Let $T_{w_{\max}}$ be the first hitting time of w_{\max} . Applying the additive drift theorem to the stopped process $w_2^{(t \wedge \tau)}$, the expected hitting time is bounded by

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{w_{\max}} \wedge \tau] \leq \frac{w_{\max}}{\frac{c}{3n}} = \frac{3nw_{\max}}{c} = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{n^2}{\log^{1+\gamma} n}\right).$$

By Markov's inequality, the probability that the hitting time of the stopped process exceeds t_{\max} is bounded by

$$\Pr(T_{w_{\max}} \wedge \tau > t_{\max}) \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[T_{w_{\max}} \wedge \tau]}{t_{\max}} \leq \frac{\mathcal{O}\left(\frac{n^2}{\log^{1+\gamma} n}\right)}{\frac{n^2}{\log^{1+\gamma/2} n}} = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^{\gamma/2} n}\right).$$

We now show that the stopping condition τ is highly unlikely to be triggered during this phase. At each step the success probability is bounded from above by $2/n$. In order to reach a fitness of $n/2 - \epsilon n$ leading ones, it is necessary that the algorithm improves at least a linear amount of times, also taking into account the one expected *free rider* per improvement i.e., the random number of 1-bits immediately following the flipped 0-bit [31]. Since at each step the success probability is bounded from above by $2/n$, by Chernoff bounds the probability of achieving a linear number of improvements within $t \leq \frac{n^2}{\log^c n}$ steps, $c > 0$ a constant, is $e^{-\Omega(n)}$.

Thus, using Lemma 2 to bound the probability that $w_1^{(t)} \geq 2w_2^{(t)}$, the probability that the stopping condition τ is triggered before or at t_{\max} is bounded by the union of the two failure probabilities,

$$\Pr(\tau \leq t_{\max}) \leq n^{-\Omega(1)} + e^{-\Omega(n)}.$$

We want to guarantee the successful event where w_2 reaches w_{\max} within t_{\max} steps and the stopping condition τ is never triggered. The complementary failure event is bounded by applying a union bound,

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(T_{w_{\max}} > t_{\max} \cup \tau \leq t_{\max}) &\leq \Pr(T_{w_{\max}} \wedge \tau > t_{\max}) + \Pr(\tau \leq t_{\max}) \\ &\leq \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^{\gamma/2} n}\right) + n^{-\Omega(1)} + e^{-\Omega(n)} = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^{\gamma/2} n}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, with probability at least $1 - \mathcal{O}(1/\log^{\gamma/2} n)$, the weight w_2 reaches w_{\max} within t_{\max} steps and the stopping condition is entirely avoided. \square

While Lemma 3 proves that the weight w_2 rapidly reaches w_{\max} , establishing a selection probability of $p_2 = 1 - o(1)$ also requires that w_1 remains comparatively small during the climbing stage of w_2 . Relying on the $o(n^2)$ time bound established in Lemma 3, we construct a non-negative supermartingale to analyze the multiplicative increase of w_1 . This will show that w_1 remains sub-polynomial, ensuring it cannot rival the magnitude of w_{\max} .

Lemma 4. *For the RLHH algorithm optimizing the LEADINGONES function with initial weights $w_1^{(0)} = w_2^{(0)} = \log n$, let τ be the first time step where $w_2^{(\tau)}$ reaches w_{\max} . At time τ , the weight w_1 is bounded by $w_1^{(\tau)} \leq \mathcal{O}(\log^2 n)$ with probability at least $1 - \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log n}\right)$.*

Proof. We divide the climbing stage of w_2 into m distinct phases demarcated by boundaries $B_k = 2^k \log n$ for $k = 0, \dots, m$. The number of phases is $m = \lceil \log_2(w_{\max}/\log n) \rceil \leq \log n$. Phase k begins when w_2 first reaches B_k and concludes when it reaches B_{k+1} .

First, we bound the probability that w_2 drops below $B_k/2$ during Phase k . We model the distance to this lower failure boundary as a process $V_t = B_k/2 - w_2^{(t)}$. At the start of the phase, $w_2 = B_k$, so $V_{t_{\text{start}}} = -B_k/2$.

By Lemma 2, with probability $1 - n^{-\Omega(1)}$, the weights satisfy $w_1^{(t)} \leq 2w_2^{(t)}$ throughout this time horizon. Conditioned on this non-dominance event, the selection probability of RLS₂ is at least

$$p_2^{(t)} = \frac{w_2^{(t)}}{w_1^{(t)} + w_2^{(t)}} \geq \frac{w_2^{(t)}}{2w_2^{(t)} + w_2^{(t)}} = \frac{1}{3}.$$

Coupling this with the conditional expected change $\Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \geq c/n$ derived in Lemma 1, the unconditional expected one-step growth of w_2 is

$$\mathbb{E}[\Delta w_2^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = p_2^{(t)} \Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{c}{n}\right) := \frac{c_2}{n},$$

for a positive constant $c_2 > 0$. Consequently, the expected one-step change of V_t is bounded by

$$\mu_t = \mathbb{E}[\Delta V_t \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = -\mathbb{E}[\Delta w_2^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq -\frac{c_2}{n} := -\mu.$$

A success increases w_2 by $\alpha = 1 + 1/\log n \leq 2$, and a failure decreases it by $\beta = 1/n$. Thus, the maximum positive change for V_t occurs when w_2 fails, yielding $\Delta V_t \leq 1/n$. The conditional variance is bounded by the second moment:

$$\text{Var}(\Delta V_t \mid \mathcal{F}_t) \leq \Pr(\text{success})\alpha^2 + \Pr(\text{failure})\beta^2 \leq \frac{2}{n}(4) + 1 \left(\frac{1}{n^2} \right) \leq \frac{c_v}{n} := \sigma^2,$$

for a constant $c_v > 0$.

To apply Freedman's inequality (Theorem 3), we define the martingale difference sequence $Y_t = \Delta V_t - \mu_t$. By definition, $\mathbb{E}[Y_t \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = 0$. Since $\Delta V_t \leq 1/n$ and $\mu_t \geq -2$, Y_t is uniformly bounded from above by $c_{\max} = 3$.

Let the maximum duration of Phase k be $t_k = \frac{2nB_k}{c_2}$ steps. The predictable quadratic variation over this period is strictly bounded by

$$V_{t_k} \leq t_k \sigma^2 = \left(\frac{2nB_k}{c_2} \right) \frac{c_v}{n} = \frac{2c_v}{c_2} B_k.$$

Let $M_j = \sum_{i=t_{\text{start}}}^{t_{\text{start}}+j-1} Y_i$. For the distance process V_t to cover the failure gap $\Delta = B_k/2$ at any step $j \leq t_k$, the martingale must exceed $M_j \geq j\mu + \Delta$. Since $\mu > 0$, this implies $M_j \geq \Delta$. Applying Freedman's inequality directly to the entire trajectory of Phase k we get,

$$\Pr\left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq t_k} M_j \geq \Delta \right) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta^2}{2(V_{t_k} + c_{\max}\Delta/3)} \right).$$

Substituting $\Delta = B_k/2$, $V_{t_k} = \frac{2c_v}{c_2} B_k$, and $c_{\max} = 3$ into the exponent yields

$$\frac{(B_k/2)^2}{2\left(\frac{2c_v}{c_2} B_k + 3(B_k/2)/3\right)} = \frac{B_k^2/4}{\left(\frac{4c_v}{c_2} + 1\right) B_k} := c_3 B_k$$

for a constant $c_3 > 0$. Thus, the probability of w_2 dropping below half the boundary at any point during the entirety of Phase k is $\exp(-c_3 B_k)$. Taking a single union bound over all $m \leq \log n$ phases, the total failure probability for the descent is $\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \exp(-c_3 2^k \log n) = n^{-\Omega(1)}$.

Next, we bound the phase duration. We allocate a maximum time limit of $t_k = \frac{2nB_k}{c_2}$ for Phase k . Because w_2 possesses an unconditional positive drift of at least c_2/n , its expected accumulated displacement over t_k steps is at least $t_k(c_2/n) = 2B_k$. For the phase to fail to conclude within t_k steps, the final displacement must be less than B_k . Using the analogous martingale difference sequence $Y'_t = (c_2/n) - \Delta w_2^{(t)}$, this failure event implies that the martingale sum over t_k steps exceeds B_k , i.e., $\sum_{i=1}^{t_k} Y'_i > B_k$.

By definition, the maximum single-step positive value for Y'_t occurs when w_2 fails and decreases by $1/n$, yielding $Y'_t \leq c_2/n - (-1/n) = (c_2 + 1)/n \leq 1 := c'_{\max}$ for sufficiently large n . The predictable quadratic variation is strictly bounded by

$$V_{t_k} \leq t_k \sigma^2 = \left(\frac{2nB_k}{c_2} \right) \frac{c_v}{n} = \frac{2c_v}{c_2} B_k.$$

Applying Freedman's inequality to the upper tail of the martingale sum, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr\left(\sum_{i=1}^{t_k} Y'_i > B_k\right) &\leq \exp\left(-\frac{B_k^2}{2(V_{t_k} + c'_{\max} B_k/3)}\right) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{B_k^2}{2(\frac{2c_v}{c_2} B_k + B_k/3)}\right) \\ &= \exp\left(-\frac{B_k}{16c_v/c_2 + 4}\right) = \exp(-c_4 B_k). \end{aligned}$$

Taking a union bound over all $m \leq \log n$ phases, the total failure probability for the duration condition across the entire climbing stage is $\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \exp(-c_4 2^k \log n) = n^{-\Omega(1)}$.

Let $\mathcal{E}_{\text{safe}}$ be the compound event that for all $m \leq \log n$ phases, the descent bound $w_2^{(t)} \geq B_k/2$ is maintained, the duration bound $\Delta T_k \leq t_k$ holds, and RLS_1 remains non-dominant. By a union bound over the descent failure ($n^{-\Omega(1)}$), duration failure ($n^{-\Omega(1)}$), and non-dominance failure ($n^{-\Omega(1)}$), we can bound the safety event by $\Pr(\mathcal{E}_{\text{safe}}) = 1 - n^{-\Omega(1)}$.

Conditioned on $\mathcal{E}_{\text{safe}}$, the selection probability of RLS_1 in Phase k is bounded by

$$p_1^{(t)} = \frac{w_1^{(t)}}{w_1^{(t)} + w_2^{(t)}} \leq \frac{w_1^{(t)}}{B_k/2}.$$

The conditional expected growth of w_1 is bounded by

$$\mathbb{E}[\Delta w_1^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = p_1^{(t)} \Delta_1^{\text{sel}} \leq w_1^{(t)} \left(\frac{2c_1}{B_k n \log n}\right) := w_1^{(t)} \cdot \delta_k.$$

This yields the one-step conditional expectation bound

$$\mathbb{E}[w_1^{(t+1)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq w_1^{(t)}(1 + \delta_k).$$

To track the expected growth over multiple steps, we take the conditional expectation of both sides with respect to the initial filtration $\mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}$ at the beginning of the phase which gives

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\mathbb{E}[w_1^{(t+1)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \mid \mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}\right] \leq \mathbb{E}\left[w_1^{(t)}(1 + \delta_k) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}\right].$$

Applying the Law of Total Expectation (Theorem 5) to the left-hand side rigorously reduces to $\mathbb{E}[w_1^{(t+1)} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}]$. Thus, we obtain the following bound for the expected value of w_1 at step $t+1$ conditioned on the initial filtration,

$$\mathbb{E}[w_1^{(t+1)} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}] \leq (1 + \delta_k) \mathbb{E}[w_1^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}] .$$

Since Phase k concludes within a maximum time limit of $t_k = \frac{2nB_k}{c_2}$ steps, iteratively unpacking this bound over t_k steps yields

$$\mathbb{E}[w_1^{(t_{\text{start}}+t_k)} \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{safe}}] \leq w_1^{(t_{\text{start}})}(1 + \delta_k)^{t_k} \leq w_1^{(t_{\text{start}})} \exp(\delta_k \cdot t_k).$$

Substituting δ_k and t_k yields the following expansion factor for Phase k ,

$$\delta_k \cdot t_k = \left(\frac{2c_1}{B_k n \log n} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{2nB_k}{c_2} \right) = \frac{4c_1}{c_2 \log n}.$$

Applying the Law of Total Expectation (Theorem 5) iteratively again across all $m \leq \log n$ phases, the expected final value of w_1 at the total duration $\tau \leq \sum t_k$ is bounded by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[w_1^{(\tau)} \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{safe}}] &\leq w_1^{(0)} \prod_{k=0}^{m-1} \exp(\delta_k t_k) \leq (\log n) \exp\left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{4c_1}{c_2 \log n}\right) \\ &\leq (\log n) \exp\left((\log n) \frac{4c_1}{c_2 \log n}\right) = \mathcal{O}(\log n). \end{aligned}$$

To bound the probability that w_1 prematurely rivals w_{\max} at any point during this stage, we observe that the expected growth establishes a submartingale relationship. By Doob's maximal inequality (Theorem 2), the conditional probability that the maximum value of w_1 reaches or exceeds $\log^2 n$ at any time $t \leq \tau$ is bounded by

$$\Pr\left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq \tau} w_1^{(t)} \geq \log^2 n \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{safe}}\right) \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[w_1^{(\tau)} \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{safe}}]}{\log^2 n} \leq \frac{\mathcal{O}(\log n)}{\log^2 n} = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log n}\right).$$

Removing the conditioning on $\mathcal{E}_{\text{safe}}$ by applying a final union bound over the submartingale failure and the safety event failure, the bound $w_1^{(t)} < \log^2 n$ holds for all $t \leq \tau$ with probability at least $1 - \mathcal{O}(1/\log n) - n^{-\Omega(1)} = 1 - \mathcal{O}(1/\log n)$. \square

To complete the analysis of Phase 1, we prove that once the weight w_2 reaches w_{\max} , it stably maintains its dominant position until the algorithm successfully reaches the fitness level $n/2$. Because the dynamics of w_1 and w_2 are coupled, we analyze them sequentially: we first unconditionally bound the maximum possible growth of w_1 assuming w_2 does not drop, and then use this established bound to prove via Freedman's maximal inequality that w_2 indeed does not experience a significant drop.

Lemma 5. *For the RLHH algorithm optimizing the LEADINGONES function with parameter $w_{\max} = \frac{n}{\log^{1+\gamma} n}$ for a constant $0 < \gamma < 1$, suppose w_2 has reached w_{\max} . With probability at least $1 - n^{-1/2+o(1)}$, the weights maintain the strict bounds $w_2^{(t)} \geq w_{\max}/2$ and $w_1^{(t)} \leq w_{\max}^{1/2}$ for all subsequent steps until Phase 1 concludes. Consequently, the selection probability robustly satisfies $p_2^{(t)} = 1 - o(1)$ throughout this entire period.*

Proof. Let t_{start} be the time step when w_2 first reaches w_{\max} . Phase 1 concludes when the algorithm reaches a fitness of $n/2$, requiring at most $n/2$ successful mutations. For any fitness level $i < n/2$, the success probabilities of

both operators are strictly lower-bounded by $1/n$ (specifically, $P_1(i) = 1/n$ and $P_2(i) \geq \frac{2(n-(n-1)/2-1)}{n(n-1)} = 1/n$). We allocate a maximum duration of $t_{\max} = c_0 n^2$ steps (e.g., $c_0 = 2$) for the remainder of Phase 1. Within this duration, the total number of successful mutations stochastically dominates a binomial distribution $\text{Bin}(2n^2, 1/n)$, which yields an expected value of $\mu = 2n$ successes. Applying the Chernoff bound (Theorem 1), the probability of obtaining fewer than $n/2$ successes (i.e., failing to conclude Phase 1 within t_{\max} steps) is bounded by

$$\Pr(X < n/2) = \Pr\left(X < \left(1 - \frac{3}{4}\right)\mu\right) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{(3/4)^2 \cdot 2n}{2}\right) = e^{-\Omega(n)}.$$

We analyze the interval $t \in [t_{\text{start}}, t_{\text{start}} + t_{\max}]$.

We introduce a stopping time τ_{drop} defined as the first time step where $w_2^{(t)} < w_{\max}/2$. We first analyze the multiplicative growth of w_1 up to time $\min(t_{\text{start}} + t_{\max}, \tau_{\text{drop}})$. In this interval, we have $w_2^{(t)} \geq w_{\max}/2$, yielding $p_1^{(t)} \leq \frac{w_1^{(t)}}{w_{\max}/2}$. Using $\Delta_1^{\text{sel}} \leq \frac{c_1}{n \log n}$ from Lemma 1, the conditional expected growth of w_1 is bounded by

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\Delta w_1^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] = p_1^{(t)} \Delta_1^{\text{sel}} \leq w_1^{(t)} \left(\frac{2c_1}{w_{\max} n \log n}\right) := w_1^{(t)} \cdot \delta.$$

This yields the one-step conditional expectation bound $\mathbb{E}[w_1^{(t+1)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq w_1^{(t)}(1 + \delta)$. To track the growth of w_1 systematically from the beginning of this phase, we take the conditional expectation of both sides strictly with respect to the initial filtration $\mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}$. Applying the Law of Total Expectation (Theorem 5), we have

$$\mathbb{E}\left[w_1^{(t+1)} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}\right] \leq (1 + \delta)\mathbb{E}\left[w_1^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}\right].$$

Iterating this recurrence over the maximum allocated duration $t_{\max} = c_0 n^2$, the expected terminal value of w_1 is bounded by

$$\mathbb{E}\left[w_1^{(t_{\text{start}}+t_{\max})} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}\right] \leq w_1^{(t_{\text{start}})}(1 + \delta)^{t_{\max}} \leq w_1^{(t_{\text{start}})} \exp(\delta \cdot t_{\max}).$$

Substituting $w_{\max} = \frac{n}{\log^{1+\gamma} n}$, the exponent evaluates exactly to

$$\delta \cdot t_{\max} = \left(\frac{2c_1 \log^{1+\gamma} n}{n^2 \log n}\right) \cdot (c_0 n^2) = 2c_0 c_1 \log^\gamma n.$$

Because the parameter strictly satisfies $\gamma \in (0, 1)$, this exponent is sub-logarithmic, guaranteeing that the expansion factor is bounded by $\exp(2c_0 c_1 \log^\gamma n) = n^{o(1)}$. Coupling this bound with the initial condition $w_1^{(t_{\text{start}})} \leq \mathcal{O}(\log^2 n)$ previously established in Lemma 4, the overall conditional expectation is tightly bounded by

$$\mathbb{E}\left[w_1^{(t_{\text{start}}+t_{\max})} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t_{\text{start}}}\right] \leq \mathcal{O}(\log^2 n) \cdot n^{o(1)} = n^{o(1)}.$$

Then we apply Doob's maximal inequality (Theorem 2). The probability that the maximum value of w_1 reaches or exceeds $w_{\max}^{1/2} = \frac{n^{1/2}}{\log^{(1+\gamma)/2} n}$ at any time before $\min(t_{\text{start}} + t_{\max}, \tau_{\text{drop}})$ is rigorously bounded by

$$\Pr\left(\max_{t_{\text{start}} \leq t \leq t_{\text{start}} + t_{\max}} w_1^{(t)} \geq w_{\max}^{1/2}\right) \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}\left[w_1^{(t_{\text{start}} + t_{\max})}\right]}{w_{\max}^{1/2}} \leq \frac{n^{o(1)}}{n^{1/2}/\log^{(1+\gamma)/2} n} = n^{-1/2+o(1)}.$$

Let \mathcal{E}_{w_1} be the event that $w_1^{(t)} \leq w_{\max}^{1/2}$ is successfully maintained for all t_{\max} steps.

Conditioning on \mathcal{E}_{w_1} , we bound the drop probability of w_2 . Throughout the interval, the selection probability of RLS₂ is robustly bounded from below by

$$p_2^{(t)} = \frac{w_2^{(t)}}{w_1^{(t)} + w_2^{(t)}} \geq \frac{w_{\max}/2}{w_{\max}^{1/2} + w_{\max}/2} = 1 - \mathcal{O}\left(w_{\max}^{-1/2}\right) \geq 1/2.$$

Even as the fitness approaches $n/2$, the success probability $P_2(i)$ is lower-bounded by $1/n$. Thus we have $\Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \geq \Delta_1^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{1}{n \log n}$. Therefore, the unconditional one-step expected change is $\mathbb{E}[\Delta w_2^{(t)} | \mathcal{F}_t] = p_2^{(t)} \Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{n \log n}\right)$.

We model the distance from the upper bound as $V_t = w_{\max} - w_2^{(t)}$. The expected one-step change is

$$\mu_t = \mathbb{E}[\Delta V_t | \mathcal{F}_t] = -\mathbb{E}[\Delta w_2^{(t)} | \mathcal{F}_t] \leq -\frac{1}{2n \log n} := -\mu.$$

A success increases w_2 by at most $\alpha < 2$, and a failure decreases it by $\beta = 1/n$. Thus, the maximum positive change for V_t is $\Delta V_t \leq 1/n$. The conditional variance is bounded by $\sigma^2 = \frac{c_3}{n}$ for a constant $c_3 > 0$. We define the martingale difference sequence $Y_t = \Delta V_t - \mu_t$, which is uniformly bounded from above by $c_{\max} = 3$.

To drop below $w_{\max}/2$ within $t_{\max} = c_0 n^2$ steps, the distance process V_t must cover a gap of $\Delta = w_{\max}/2$. Since the drift is strictly negative ($\mu > 0$), for $V_t \geq \Delta$ to occur at any step $j \leq t_{\max}$, the martingale sum $M_j = \sum_{i=1}^j Y_i$ must completely overcome this drift, requiring $M_j \geq j\mu + \Delta \geq \Delta$. Thus, triggering τ_{drop} requires $\max_{1 \leq j \leq t_{\max}} M_j \geq \Delta$.

The predictable quadratic variation over the maximum duration t_{\max} is strictly bounded by

$$v = t_{\max} \sigma^2 = (c_0 n^2) \left(\frac{c_3}{n}\right) = c_0 c_3 n.$$

Applying Freedman's inequality (Theorem 3) directly to the entire trajectory of V_t ,

$$\Pr\left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq t_{\max}} M_j \geq \Delta\right) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta^2}{2(v + c_{\max} \Delta/3)}\right).$$

Substituting $\Delta = \frac{n}{2 \log^{1+\gamma} n}$, $v = c_0 c_3 n$, and $c_{\max} = 3$ into the exponent yields

$$\frac{\Delta^2}{2(v + c_{\max} \Delta/3)} = \frac{\frac{n^2}{4 \log^{2+2\gamma} n}}{2 \left(c_0 c_3 n + \frac{n}{2 \log^{1+\gamma} n} \right)} \geq \frac{c_4 n}{\log^{2+2\gamma} n}$$

for a constant $c_4 > 0$. Thus, the probability that w_2 triggers τ_{drop} by ever dropping below $w_{\max}/2$ during the entire period is bounded by $e^{-\Omega(n/\log^{2+2\gamma} n)}$.

To complete the proof, we take a final union bound over the three independent failure events. Phase 1 failing to conclude within t_{\max} steps with probability $e^{-\Omega(n)}$, w_2 dropping below $w_{\max}/2$ with probability $e^{-\Omega(n/\log^{2+2\gamma} n)}$, and w_1 exceeding $w_{\max}^{1/2}$ with probability $n^{-1/2+o(1)}$. The sum of these failure probabilities is strictly dominated by the polynomial term $n^{-1/2+o(1)}$. Thus, with probability at least $1 - n^{-1/2+o(1)}$, both weight bounds hold uninterruptedly until Phase 1 concludes, which directly guarantees that the selection probability maintains $p_2^{(t)} = 1 - \mathcal{O}(w_{\max}^{-1/2}) = 1 - o(1)$ throughout the entire period. \square

We now prove the main result for Phase 1.

Theorem 6. *For the RLHH algorithm optimizing the LEADINGONES function, let T_{phase1} be the total number of fitness evaluations required to reach a fitness of at least $n/2$ from a uniformly distributed random initial string. The expected runtime is strictly bounded by*

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{phase1}}] = T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} + o(n^2),$$

where $T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}}$ is the expected runtime for the theoretically optimal RLS₂ algorithm to traverse the same fitness distance.

Proof. We condition the runtime analysis of Phase 1 on the successful establishment and maintenance of the exploratory regime. Let $\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}} = \mathcal{E}_{\text{climb}} \cap \mathcal{E}_{\text{maint}}$ be the compound success event. The event $\mathcal{E}_{\text{climb}}$ denotes that the weight w_2 successfully reaches w_{\max} within an overhead of $t_{\max} = \frac{n^2}{\log^{1+\gamma/2} n}$ steps. By Lemma 3, the complementary failure probability is $\Pr(\neg \mathcal{E}_{\text{climb}}) = \mathcal{O}(1/\log^{\gamma/2} n)$. The event $\mathcal{E}_{\text{maint}}$ denotes that following this initial climbing stage, the selection probability satisfies $p_2^{(t)} = 1 - o(1)$ continually until the fitness reaches $n/2$. By Lemma 5, $\Pr(\neg \mathcal{E}_{\text{maint}}) \leq n^{-1/2+o(1)}$. Applying a union bound over these two sequential phases, the compound failure probability is strictly dominated by the climbing phase: $\Pr(\neg \mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}) = \mathcal{O}(1/\log^{\gamma/2} n)$.

Conditioned on $\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}$, the total time spent in Phase 1 is bounded by the sum of the time required for the weight w_2 to reach w_{\max} and the remaining time for the algorithm to optimise the first $n/2$ leading ones. We pessimistically assume the algorithm makes zero fitness progress during the initial t_{\max} steps. Following this overhead period, the algorithm operates under the condition $p_2^{(t)} = 1 - o(1)$. For any fitness level $i < n/2$, the probability of increasing the fitness in a single

iteration is bounded from below by the probability of selecting RLS_2 and it performing a successful mutation:

$$P_{\text{succ}}(i) = p_1^{(t)} P_1(i) + p_2^{(t)} P_2(i) \geq p_2^{(t)} P_2(i) \geq (1 - o(1)) P_2(i).$$

Because the success probability at every state is at least $1 - o(1)$ times that of the theoretically optimal RLS_2 algorithm, the conditional expected time to reach fitness $n/2$, T_{plateau} , is bounded by $1 + o(1)$ times the expected runtime of the pure RLS_2 . Thus, we have:

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{plateau}} \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}] \leq \frac{1}{1 - o(1)} T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} = (1 + o(1)) T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}}.$$

The conditional expected time for Phase 1 is thus bounded by the sum of the climbing overhead and the plateau expectation:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{phase1}} \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}] &\leq t_{\text{max}} + \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{plateau}} \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}] \\ &\leq \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{n^2}{\log^{1+\gamma/2} n}\right) + (1 + o(1)) T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} \\ &= T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} + o(n^2), \end{aligned}$$

since $T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} = cn^2$ for the RLS_2 algorithm on `LEADINGONES` for some constant $c > 0$.

Finally, we apply the law of total expectation to rigorously account for the failure event $\neg\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}$. In the worst-case scenario, regardless of the weight distribution, the algorithm maintains a minimum success probability bounded by the uniform mutation probability $P_1(i) \geq 1/n$ at every step. This yields a worst-case unconditional expected hitting time bounded by $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{worst}}] \leq \sum_{i=0}^{n/2-1} n = \mathcal{O}(n^2)$. Combining the conditional branches, the unconditional expectation for Phase 1 is strictly bounded by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{phase1}}] &= \Pr(\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}) \cdot \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{phase1}} \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}] + \Pr(\neg\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}) \cdot \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{worst}}] \\ &\leq 1 \cdot (T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} + o(n^2)) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^{\gamma/2} n}\right) \cdot \mathcal{O}(n^2) \\ &= T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} + o(n^2). \end{aligned}$$

□

3.2 Dominance of RLS_1 in Phase 2

In this section, we bound the expected runtime of `RLHH` during Phase 2. For the purpose of analysis, we reset the time counter to $t = 0$ at the transition point and pessimistically consider a worst-case initial weight distribution, where $w_1^{(0)} = w_{\text{min}}$ and $w_2^{(0)} = w_{\text{max}}$.

First, Lemma 6 establishes that the algorithm can efficiently reach a sufficiently high fitness level where RLS_2 starts to lose its advantage quickly. Then, Lemma 7 proves that once the algorithm reaches this high-fitness region, at least one of the weights will rapidly hit a boundary. Once at least one boundary is hit, Lemma 5 guarantees that RLS_1 will rapidly become dominant and maintain its dominance until the end of the optimization process.

We put these lemmata together in Theorem 7 to establish that RLHH optimizes the remaining fitness levels from $n/2$ to n in expected time $T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} + o(n^2)$, where $T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}}$ is the exact expected hitting time for the pure RLS_1 algorithm to traverse this fitness distance.

Lemma 6. *For the RLHH algorithm optimizing the LEADINGONES function, assume the algorithm has reached the beginning of Phase 2 with fitness $\text{LO}(s^{(0)}) = n/2$. The expected time to reach a fitness of at least $n/2 + n/\log n$ is bounded by $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{buf}}] \leq \frac{2n^2}{\log n}$.*

Proof. We analyze the fitness interval where $n/2 \leq i < n/2 + n/\log n$. The success probability for RLS_1 in this region remains constant at $P_1(i) = \frac{1}{n}$. For RLS_2 , the success probability monotonically decreases as the fitness increases, but it is bounded from below at the upper limit of this interval:

$$P_2(i) = \frac{2(n-i-1)}{n(n-1)} \geq \frac{2(n-(n/2+n/\log n)-1)}{n(n-1)} = \frac{n-2n/\log n-2}{n(n-1)}.$$

For sufficiently large n , this establishes a uniform lower bound of $P_2(i) \geq \frac{1}{2n}$.

Regardless of the dynamic operator selection probabilities $p_1^{(t)}$ and $p_2^{(t)}$, the overall probability of achieving a successful fitness improvement in any single iteration is unconditionally lower-bounded by the worst-case operator:

$$P_{\text{succ}}(i) = p_1^{(t)} P_1(i) + p_2^{(t)} P_2(i) \geq \min(P_1(i), P_2(i)) \geq \frac{1}{2n}.$$

Let $D = n/\log n$ denote the required number of fitness levels to cross this interval. Pessimistically assuming that each successful mutation increases the fitness by exactly 1, the expected time spent at any single fitness level i within this interval is at most $\frac{1}{P_{\text{succ}}(i)} \leq 2n$.

Applying the Fitness Level Method [39], the total expected time T_{buf} to traverse this entire intermediate interval is bounded by the sum of the expected times spent at each level:

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{buf}}] \leq \sum_{i=n/2}^{n/2+n/\log n-1} \frac{1}{P_{\text{succ}}(i)} \leq \sum_{i=n/2}^{n/2+n/\log n-1} 2n = \left(\frac{n}{\log n}\right) \cdot 2n = \frac{2n^2}{\log n}.$$

□

We now bound the expected time required for either weight to reach its boundary.

Lemma 7. *For the RLHH algorithm optimizing the LEADINGONES function, assume the algorithm has reached the beginning of Phase 2 with fitness $\text{LO}(s^{(0)}) = n/2$. Let τ be the first time step where either the condition $w_1^{(t)} = w_{\max}$ or $w_2^{(t)} = w_{\min}$ is triggered. The expected hitting time is bounded by $\mathbb{E}[\tau] = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{n^2}{\log^\gamma n}\right)$.*

Proof. By Lemma 6, the algorithm reaches a fitness of at least $n/2 + n/\log n$ in expected time $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{buf}}] \leq \frac{2n^2}{\log n}$. We analyze the subsequent dynamics starting from this point.

For any fitness level $i \geq n/2 + n/\log n$, the success probability of RLS₁ is $P_1(i) = 1/n$. By Lemma 1, its conditional expected change is bounded by $\Delta_1^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{c_1}{n \log n}$ for a constant $c_1 > 0$. For RLS₂, the success probability is bounded by

$$P_2(i) = \frac{2(n-i-1)}{n(n-1)} \leq \frac{2(n-(n/2+n/\log n))}{n^2} = \frac{1}{n} - \frac{2}{n \log n}.$$

Incorporating the reward parameter $\alpha = 1 + 1/\log n$ and the penalty parameter $\beta = 1/n$, the conditional drift Δ_2^{sel} evaluates to

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_2^{\text{sel}} &= P_2(i)\alpha - (1 - P_2(i))\beta = P_2(i)(\alpha + \beta) - \beta \\ &\leq \left(\frac{1}{n} - \frac{2}{n \log n}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{\log n} + \frac{1}{n}\right) - \frac{1}{n} \\ &= \frac{1}{n} - \frac{2}{n \log n} + \frac{1}{n \log n} - \frac{2}{n \log^2 n} + \frac{1}{n^2} - \frac{2}{n^2 \log n} - \frac{1}{n} \\ &\leq -\frac{c_2}{n \log n}, \end{aligned}$$

for a constant $c_2 \in (0, 1)$ and sufficiently large n .

To rigorously analyze the weight separation, we define a composite distance process that sums the distances of both weights to their respective target boundaries:

$$D_t = (w_{\max} - w_1^{(t)}) + (w_2^{(t)} - w_{\min}).$$

For all $t < \tau$, neither boundary has been reached, guaranteeing $w_1^{(t)} < w_{\max}$ and $w_2^{(t)} > w_{\min}$, which yields $D_t > 0$. The initial distance is bounded by $D_0 \leq 2w_{\max}$. The expected one-step decrease of D_t given the filtration \mathcal{F}_t for $t < \tau$ isolates the combined selection probabilities,

$$\mathbb{E}[D_t - D_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = \mathbb{E}[\Delta w_1^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] - \mathbb{E}[\Delta w_2^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = p_1^{(t)} \Delta_1^{\text{sel}} - p_2^{(t)} \Delta_2^{\text{sel}}.$$

Since $\Delta_1^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{c_1}{n \log n}$ and $-\Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{c_2}{n \log n}$, letting $c = \min(c_1, c_2) > 0$, we obtain the uniform lower bound on the expected drift,

$$\mathbb{E}[D_t - D_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \geq p_1^{(t)} \left(\frac{c}{n \log n}\right) + p_2^{(t)} \left(\frac{c}{n \log n}\right) = \frac{c}{n \log n} (p_1^{(t)} + p_2^{(t)}) = \frac{c}{n \log n}.$$

This drift holds as long as neither weight has reached its respective boundary because otherwise one of the two weights cannot change in value anymore. Let T_0

be time needed to reach $D_t \leq 0$. Applying the additive drift theorem (Theorem 4) to D_t , we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}[T_0] \leq \frac{D_0}{\frac{c}{n \log n}} \leq \frac{2w_{\max}}{\frac{c}{n \log n}} = \frac{2n \log n}{c} \cdot \frac{n}{\log^{1+\gamma} n} = \frac{2n^2}{c \log^\gamma n}.$$

Thus, the expected time to hit at least one of the boundaries is $\mathbb{E}[\tau] \leq \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{buf}}] + \mathbb{E}[T_0] \leq \frac{2n^2}{\log n} + \frac{2n^2}{c \log^\gamma n} = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{n^2}{\log^\gamma n}\right)$. \square

In the following lemma, we prove that once either weight hits its respective boundary, the system rapidly stabilizes into a new regime that strictly favors RLS_1 (e.g., $p_1 = 1 - o(1)$).

Lemma 8. *For the RLHH algorithm optimizing the LEADINGONES function, suppose at time τ the weights satisfy either $w_1^{(\tau)} = w_{\max}$ or $w_2^{(\tau)} = w_{\min}$. With probability at least $1 - \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}\right)$, within an additional $t_{\text{stab}} = \frac{n^2}{\log^{\gamma/2} n}$ steps, the algorithm establishes a dominance regime where the selection probability of RLS_1 satisfies $p_1^{(t)} = 1 - o(1)$, and this regime is maintained until Phase 2 concludes.*

Proof. For any fitness level $i \geq n/2 + n/\log n$, the drift analysis in Lemma 7 establishes conditional expected changes bounded by $\Delta_1^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{c_1}{n \log n} > 0$ and $\Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \leq -\frac{c_2}{n \log n} < 0$. Because Δ_2^{sel} is strictly negative, the expected one-step change is $\mathbb{E}[\Delta w_2^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = p_2^{(t)} \Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \leq 0$. This fundamental property ensures that $w_2^{(t)}$ unconditionally acts as a non-negative supermartingale throughout this region.

We consider the two possible boundary cases separately.

Case 1: w_1 hits the upper bound ($w_1^{(\tau)} = w_{\max}$). Let $t_{\max} = c_0 n^2$ for a sufficiently large constant $c_0 > 0$. We define τ^* as the first time step strictly after τ where $w_1^{(t)} < w_{\max}/2$.

For all time steps within the stopped window $t \in [\tau, \min(\tau^*, \tau + t_{\max}))$, we have $w_1^{(t)} \geq w_{\max}/2$. Since $w_2^{(t)} \leq w_{\max}$, the selection probability of RLS_1 is rigorously lower-bounded by $p_1^{(t)} \geq \frac{w_{\max}/2}{w_{\max}/2 + w_{\max}} = 1/3$.

We first bound the probability of w_1 dropping. Applying the exact same martingale analysis and Freedman's inequality as established in the proof of Lemma 5, the probability of w_1 dropping below $w_{\max}/2$ within t_{\max} steps is bounded by

$$\Pr\left(\min_{\tau \leq t \leq \tau + t_{\max}} w_1^{(t)} < w_{\max}/2\right) \leq e^{-\Omega(n/\log^{2+2\gamma} n)}.$$

Thus, $w_1^{(t)} \geq w_{\max}/2$ holds with high probability for the required duration.

Next, we prove that Phase 2 successfully concludes within t_{\max} steps. The probability of achieving a successful mutation at any step is $P_{\text{succ}}(i) \geq p_1^{(t)} P_1(i) \geq$

$\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{n} = \frac{1}{3n}$ and the algorithm requires at most $n/2$ successes to reach the global optimum. Within $t_{\max} = c_0 n^2$ steps, the expected number of successes is at least $c_0 n/3$. By selecting $c_0 \geq 3$, Chernoff bounds guarantee that the probability of obtaining fewer than $n/2$ successes is exponentially small, bounded by $e^{-\Omega(n)}$. By a union bound, with probability at least $1 - e^{-\Omega(n/\log^{2+2\gamma} n)} - e^{-\Omega(n)} = 1 - e^{-\Omega(n/\log^{2+2\gamma} n)}$, the weight w_1 does not drop below $w_{\max}/2$ until the algorithm reaches the global optimum.

Conditioned on this lower bound for w_1 , we now analyze the rapid suppression of w_2 . The selection probability of RLS₂ satisfies $p_2^{(t)} = \frac{w_2^{(t)}}{w_1^{(t)} + w_2^{(t)}} \geq \frac{w_2^{(t)}}{2w_{\max}}$, which gives the following bound:

$$\mathbb{E}[w_2^{(t)} - w_2^{(t+1)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = -p_2^{(t)} \Delta_2^{\text{sel}} \geq \frac{w_2^{(t)}}{2w_{\max}} \left(\frac{c_2}{n \log n} \right) = w_2^{(t)} \frac{c_2 \log^\gamma n}{2n^2} := w_2^{(t)} \delta$$

Applying the Law of Total Expectation (Theorem 5), the expected value of w_2 at time $\tau + t_{\text{stab}}$ is exponentially bounded by:

$$\mathbb{E}[w_2^{(\tau+t_{\text{stab}})}] \leq w_{\max} (1-\delta)^{t_{\text{stab}}} \leq w_{\max} \exp(-t_{\text{stab}} \delta) = w_{\max} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2}{2} \log^{\gamma/2} n\right).$$

Then we apply Markov's inequality to the state value at time $\tau + t_{\text{stab}}$ to rigorously bound the probability that w_2 fails to drop below a strict intermediate target $w_{\text{target}} = w_{\max}/\log^4 n$,

$$\Pr\left(w_2^{(\tau+t_{\text{stab}})} \geq \frac{w_{\max}}{\log^4 n}\right) \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[w_2^{(\tau+t_{\text{stab}})}]}{w_{\max}/\log^4 n} \leq \log^4 n \cdot \exp\left(-\Omega(\log^{\gamma/2} n)\right).$$

Thus, with probability at least $1 - \log^4 n \cdot e^{-\Omega(\log^{\gamma/2} n)}$, w_2 successfully drops below the target $w_{\max}/\log^4 n$ within t_{stab} steps. For the remaining duration after time $\tau + t_{\text{stab}}$, applying Doob's maximal inequality to the supermartingale $w_2^{(t)}$ (Theorem 2) strictly limits the probability of it returning back to $w_{\max}/\log^2 n$ to at most:

$$\Pr\left(\sup_{t \geq \tau+t_{\text{stab}}} w_2^{(t)} \geq \frac{w_{\max}}{\log^2 n}\right) \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[w_2^{(\tau+t_{\text{stab}})}]}{w_{\max}/\log^2 n} \leq \frac{w_{\max}/\log^4 n}{w_{\max}/\log^2 n} = \frac{1}{\log^2 n}.$$

By a union bound, with probability at least $1 - e^{-\Omega(n/\log^{2+2\gamma} n)} - \log^4 n \cdot e^{-\Omega(\log^{\gamma/2} n)} - \frac{1}{\log^2 n} = 1 - \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}\right)$, within an additional $t_{\text{stab}} = \frac{n^2}{\log^{\gamma/2} n}$ steps, the selection probability of RLS₁ satisfies $p_1^{(t)} \geq \frac{w_{\max}/2}{w_{\max}/2 + w_{\max}/\log^2 n} = 1 - o(1)$, and this dominance is maintained until Phase 2 concludes.

Case 2: w_2 hits the lower bound ($w_2^{(\tau)} = w_{\min}$). Since w_{\min} is a constant, applying Doob's maximal inequality to the supermartingale $w_2^{(t)}$ starting from w_{\min} , the probability that it reaches $\log^2 n$ is bounded by

$$\Pr\left(\sup_{t \geq \tau} w_2^{(t)} \geq \log^2 n\right) \leq \frac{w_{\min}}{\log^2 n} = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}\right).$$

Thus, $w_2^{(t)} < \log^2 n$ holds with probability at least $1 - \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}\right)$.

Conditioned on $w_2^{(t)} < \log^2 n$, we bound the time T_{up} required for w_1 to reach $(n \log^\gamma n)^{1/2}$. The selection probability of RLS_1 is lower-bounded by $p_1^{(t)} \geq \frac{w_{\min}}{w_{\min} + \log^2 n} = \Omega(1/\log^2 n)$. Thus the expected change of w_1 is

$$\mathbb{E}[\Delta w_1^{(t)} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = p_1^{(t)} \Delta_1^{\text{sel}} = \Omega\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}\right) \left(\frac{c_1}{n \log n}\right) = \Omega\left(\frac{1}{n \log^3 n}\right).$$

Applying the Additive Drift Theorem, the expected time is bounded by:

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{up}}] \leq \frac{(n \log^\gamma n)^{1/2}}{\Omega\left(\frac{1}{n \log^3 n}\right)} = \mathcal{O}\left(n^{3/2} \log^{3+\gamma/2} n\right).$$

Applying Markov's inequality, the probability that w_1 fails to reach $(n \log^\gamma n)^{1/2}$ within $t_{\text{stab}} = \frac{n^2}{\log^{\gamma/2} n}$ steps is:

$$\Pr(T_{\text{up}} \geq t_{\text{stab}}) \leq \frac{\mathcal{O}\left(n^{3/2} \log^{3+\gamma/2} n\right)}{\frac{n^2}{\log^{\gamma/2} n}} = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{\log^{3+\gamma} n}{n^{1/2}}\right).$$

Once w_1 reaches $(n \log^\gamma n)^{1/2}$, using freedman inequality with same analysis as showned in the proof of Lemma 5, we can show that it remains above $(n \log^\gamma n)^{1/2}/2$ with probability at least $1 - e^{-\Omega(\log^\gamma n)}$.

Thus, with probability at least $1 - \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}\right) - \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{\log^{3+\gamma} n}{n^{1/2}}\right) - e^{-\Omega(\log^\gamma n)} = 1 - \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}\right)$, within $t_{\text{stab}} = \frac{n^2}{\log^{\gamma/2} n}$ steps after τ , the selection probability of RLS_1 satisfies $p_1^{(t)} \geq \frac{(n \log^\gamma n)^{1/2}/2}{(n \log^\gamma n)^{1/2}/2 + \log^2 n} = 1 - o(1)$, and this dominance is maintained until Phase 2 concludes.

Combining the two cases, with overall probability at least $1 - \mathcal{O}(1/\log^2 n)$, within t_{stab} steps after τ , $p_1^{(t)}$ satisfies the desired bound (e.g., $p_1 = 1 - o(1)$) and this dominance is maintained until Phase 2 concludes. \square

We now prove the main result for Phase 2.

Theorem 7. *For the RLHH algorithm optimizing the LEADINGONES function, let T_{phase2} be the total number of fitness evaluations required to reach the global optimum $\text{LO}(s) = n$ starting from a fitness of $n/2$. The expected runtime is strictly bounded by*

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{phase2}}] = T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} + o(n^2),$$

where $T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}}$ is the exact expected hitting time for the theoretically optimal pure RLS_1 algorithm to traverse the second half of the search space.

Proof. By Lemma 7, the expected time for the weights to hit at least one boundary is bounded by $\mathbb{E}[\tau] = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{n^2}{\log^\gamma n}\right)$.

By Lemma 8, conditioned on hitting the boundary, with probability at least $1 - \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}\right)$, within an additional $t_{\text{stab}} = \frac{n^2}{\log^{7/2} n}$ steps, the selection probability of RLS_1 satisfies $p_1^{(t)} = 1 - o(1)$, and this dominance is maintained until Phase 2 concludes. Let $\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}$ denote this event. We have $\Pr(\neg\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}) = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}\right)$.

Thus, conditioned on $\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}$, the expected time to reach $p_1^{(t)} = 1 - o(1)$ is $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{good}}] = \mathbb{E}[\tau] + t_{\text{stab}} = o(n^2)$ and the algorithm operates under the condition $p_1^{(t)} = 1 - o(1)$ which implies that the probability of a successful mutation at fitness level i is bounded by

$$P_{\text{succ}}(i) = p_1^{(t)} P_1(i) + p_2^{(t)} P_2(i) \geq p_1^{(t)} P_1(i) \geq (1 - o(1)) P_1(i).$$

Because the success probability at every remaining step is at least $1 - o(1)$ times that of the theoretically optimal RLS_1 algorithm, the conditional expected time to traverse the remaining fitness levels from $i = n/2$ to $n - 1$ is bounded by $1 + o(1)$ times the expected runtime of pure RLS_1 . Consequently, the total conditional expected time for Phase 2 is bounded by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{phase2}} \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}] &\leq \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{good}} \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}] + \frac{1}{1 - o(1)} T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} \\ &\leq o(n^2) + (1 + o(1)) T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} \\ &= T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} + o(n^2), \end{aligned}$$

since $T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} = \frac{1}{4} n^2$ for the RLS_1 algorithm to traverse the second half of the search space.

Next, we bound the expected runtime for the failure event $\neg\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}$. We pessimistically assume the algorithm consistently selects the operator RLS_2 for all steps up to $n - 2$. For the final step $i = n - 1$, since $P_2(i = n - 1) = 0$, progress relies entirely on RLS_1 , which is selected with a guaranteed minimum probability of $\frac{w_{\min}}{w_{\min} + w_{\max}}$. This yields a worst-case expected sprint time bounded by

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{worst}}] \leq \sum_{i=n/2}^{n-2} \frac{1}{P_2(i)} + \frac{1}{P_1(i = n - 1)} \cdot \frac{w_{\min} + w_{\max}}{w_{\min}} = \mathcal{O}(n^2 \log n).$$

The unconditional expected runtime for Phase 2 is subsequently bounded by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{phase2}}] &= \Pr(\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}) \cdot \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{phase2}} \mid \mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}] + \Pr(\neg\mathcal{E}_{\text{good}}) \cdot \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{worst}}] \\ &\leq 1 \cdot (T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} + o(n^2)) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}\right) \cdot \mathcal{O}(n^2 \log n) \\ &= T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} + o(n^2) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{n^2}{\log n}\right) \\ &= T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} + o(n^2). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

3.3 Total Expected Runtime

In this subsection, we summarize the runtime analyses of Phase 1 and Phase 2 to establish the overall expected runtime of the RLHH algorithm. We show that the weight adaptation successfully matches the performance of the theoretically optimal operator sequence, accumulating only a sub-quadratic time overhead across the entire optimization process.

Theorem 8. *For the RLHH algorithm optimizing the LEADINGONES function, let T be the total number of fitness evaluations required to reach the global optimum $\text{LO}(s) = n$ from a uniformly distributed random initial string. The expected runtime is strictly bounded by*

$$\mathbb{E}[T] = T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} + T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} + o(n^2) = \frac{1 + \ln 2}{4}n^2 + o(n^2).$$

Proof. The total runtime T is the exact sum of the time spent reaching a fitness of $n/2$ (Phase 1) and the time spent reaching the global optimum n starting from $n/2$ (Phase 2). By definition, $T = T_{\text{phase1}} + T_{\text{phase2}}$.

By the linearity of expectation, we have $\mathbb{E}[T] = \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{phase1}}] + \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{phase2}}]$. Substituting the established bounds from Theorem 6 and Theorem 7, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[T] &= (T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} + o(n^2)) + (T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} + o(n^2)) \\ &= T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} + T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} + o(n^2). \end{aligned}$$

As established in the rigorous analysis of optimal operator sequences for LEADINGONES by Lissovoi et al. [31], the expected traversal times for the optimal operators in their respective phases evaluate to $T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2}} = \frac{\ln 2}{4}n^2 + o(n)$ and $T_{\text{OPT}_{n/2 \rightarrow n}} = \frac{1}{4}n^2$. Summing these precisely yields

$$\mathbb{E}[T] = \frac{\ln 2}{4}n^2 + \frac{1}{4}n^2 + o(n^2) = \frac{1 + \ln 2}{4}n^2 + o(n^2).$$

This concludes the proof. □

4 Experimental Evaluation

In this section, we empirically evaluate the performance of the RLHH algorithm on the LEADINGONES function for realistic problem sizes and compare it against the Greedy Random Gradient (GRG) HH which also has optimal expected runtime up to lower order terms [31]. We equip both HHs with the heuristic set $H = \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$.

We simulate the algorithms across a wide range of problem sizes, from $n = 10^3$ to $n = 9 \cdot 10^9$ and for each problem size we take the average number of function evaluations over 700 runs. To allow to experiment with large problem sizes we apply the same inverse transform sampling method previously used for

Fig. 1. Average runtime normalized by n^2 for the RLHH algorithm ($\gamma \in \{0.9, 1.0\}$) compared against GRG, RLS_1 , and the theoretical 2-opt optimal strategy on the LEADINGONES function.

GRG in [31] and sample the expected waiting times to make an improvement of exactly d bits, for all possible values of d and for each operator instead of executing the operator itself.

For the RLHH algorithm, we utilize the theoretically derived parameter settings: $\alpha = 1 + 1/\log n$, $\beta = 1/n$, initial weights $w_1^{(0)} = w_2^{(0)} = \log n$, and the upper bound $w_{\max} = n/\log^{1+\gamma} n$. Our theoretical analysis indicates that w_{\max} should be as small as possible, thus γ as close as 1 as possible. This respectively decreases the runtimes derived in lemmata 3, 7 and 8 and the relevant failure probabilities. Indeed, preliminary tuning confirms this for these problem sizes. Thus, we test the algorithm with $\gamma = 0.9$ and $\gamma = 1.0$. For the GRG we set $\tau = 0.6n \ln n$ which provided the best performance in Lissovoi et al. [31].

Figure 1 displays the average runtime normalized by n^2 (i.e., the leading constants) versus the problem size. We observe that the runtimes of all three algorithms exhibit a clear, monotonic downward trend, steadily approaching the best possible expected runtime using the two operators of $\frac{1+\ln 2}{4}n^2 \approx 0.423n^2$ (i.e., 2-opt indicated in blue). The theoretical performance of the best randomised local search heuristic for the problem (i.e. RLS_1 with expected runtime $0.5n^2$) is depicted in yellow.

The configuration $\gamma = 1.0$ has the best average runtime, consistently outperforming GRG for all problem sizes greater than $n = 2 \cdot 10^3$. For the largest problem size, $n = 9 \cdot 10^9$, the two algorithms have average runtimes of $0.425n^2$ and $0.426n^2$ slightly larger than the best possible $0.423n^2$. While our formal proof conservatively requires $\gamma < 1$ to mathematically guarantee that $w_1 = o(w_{\max})$ at the conclusion of Phase 1, the practical growth rate of the weight (bounded by $e^{c \log^\gamma n}$) is sufficiently slow. Consequently, the experiments indicate that setting

$\gamma = 1.0$ provides an excellent balance between rapid weight adaptation and the stability of the dominance regimes in practice. On the other hand, the configuration with $\gamma = 0.9$ consistently outperforms the other two algorithms for smaller problem sizes and eventually becomes only slightly worse than GRG.

The only other reinforcement learning heuristic for which a theoretical runtime analysis is available is the theory-driven designed one introduced by Doerr et al. [14]. The authors proved optimal performance for ONEMAX and provided experiments for LEADINGONES. The best average runtime they reported with their chosen parameters is $0.45n^2$ for $n = 10^4$ which is beaten by all three algorithms in Figure 1.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a rigorous runtime analysis of the Reinforcement Learning Hyper-heuristic (RLHH) for the standard LEADINGONES benchmark function. This is the first time a hyper-heuristic using a reinforcement learning mechanism from the literature with a proper set of parameters is rigorously analysed. The only previous theoretical analysis had considered the RLHH equipped with only one useful operator having positive improvement probability [2]. The authors proved that RLHH is ineffective for LEADINGONES by showing that its behaviour is similar to that of a Simple Random HH that at each step selects an operator uniformly at random (i.e. the algorithm does not learn to identify the only good operator).

Our mathematical analysis proves that RLHH equipped with a low-level heuristic set $H = \{RLS_1, RLS_2\}$ and appropriate parameter values optimises LEADINGONES in an expected runtime of $\frac{1+\ln 2}{4}n^2 + o(n^2)$ perfectly matching, up to the leading constant, the best possible offline-designed sequence of these operators. The proof of the result relies on tracking the stochastic weight dynamics via various martingale inequalities and drift analyses. An empirical analysis shows that the algorithm is effective for realistic problem sizes even outperforming the Generalised Random Gradient (GRG) HH previously shown to also have optimal expected runtime.

Future research should extend the analysis to larger heuristic set sizes and to wider classes of functions. Furthermore the comparative performance using alternative update and selection rules from the literature should also be analysed such as multiplicative updates or the *max choice* selection rule.

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